

and varietal resistance screening programs at IRRI (see figure). The rearing cycle began with the adult. Four oviposition cage designs were tested in a non-airconditioned room offering a range of relative humidities (RH) to determine the optimal requirements for maximum egg production. Egg production was highest in an aerated cage design at 83-87% RH (see table). We used a mylar plastic cylinder cage (25-cm diameter and 54-cm high with mesh top, side windows, and sleeves) immersed in water. The females oviposited on the undersides of cut rice leaves floating on the water. About 30 10-cm-long leaves, cut from 3-week-old IR36 plants, were individually placed on the water leaving about 1-cm distance between them to provide room for females to oviposit.

Forty pairs of moths, placed in the oviposition cage, produced about 5,400 eggs in 4 days. Neither sugar nor other sustenance for the moths increased egg production. The leaves were replaced every day; those with eggs were held in shallow egg-holding trays with the eggs submerged. Eggs hatched in 3 days and the larvae fed on the cut leaves. To maintain the culture, 3% of the eggs (about 160) were introduced into the larval rearing cage to produce the 80 adults.

The larval rearing cage is a wooden frame with mesh sides. It was set in a metal tray containing 12 cm water. Larvae pupated on the leaf sheaths in 17-20 days. At pupation, the pots

Procedure for mass-rearing the rice caseworm on rice plants in the greenhouse. IRRI, 1979.

containing eight plants each, were removed and placed in an adult emergence cage. The tops of the plants were cut so that the emerging moths

would rest on the sides of the cage rather than on the plants and thus could readily be collected. The adults emerged in about 1 week. ■

Comparison of four oviposition cage designs for maximum caseworm egg production. IRRI, 1979.

Cage design	Eggs/female ^a (no.)	RH (%) ^b inside cage
Nylon mesh (fully aerated)	105 a	83
Mylar plastic cylinder with top and side mesh	136 a	84
Mylar plastic cylinder with top mesh only	133 a	87
Mylar plastic cylinder (enclosed)	67 b	91

^a Av of 5 replications, 15-18 females and 15-22 males/cage. In a column, means followed by a common letter are not significantly different ($P \leq 0.05$). ^b Recorded at midday; ambient room RH = 76%.

Improvement of tidal swamp rices through induced mutation

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Seeds of 9 rice cultivars from the tidal swamps of South Kalimantan, Indonesia, were treated with

ethyleneimine at 2 concentrations (0.2% and 0.4%) for 1 hour and 3 hours to induce earliness and short stature without affecting tolerance of tidal swamp conditions. The correlation of germination of M_1 seeds and spikelet fertility was positive and was helpful in identifying optimal treatments for further experiments. Single panicles selected from M_1 plants from the 2 effective treatments (0.2%, 3 h and 0.4%, 3 h) produced 1,844 M_2 progenies for further screening.

In the M_2 , the seedling mutants segregated in a simple Mendelian ratio

of 3:1. Screening of the M_2 families under natural long-day conditions in the 1979 dry season facilitated selection of photoperiod-insensitive types from Siyam Halus mutations (IR29386) and of mutants intermediate in plant height but sensitive to photoperiod from Siyam Kuning (IR30446) (see photo).

The early mutants, simultaneously raised in the wet season as M_3 plant progenies, bred true for earliness; they matured about 1 month earlier than the parents, even under short-day conditions. The early and intermediate-statured mutants were also about a

The characteristics of the tidal swamp variety Siyam Kuning (right, foreground) contrast sharply with the erect leaves and short stature of derivatives obtained through treatment with ethyleneimine.

month shorter in growth duration and about 35 cm shorter in plant height, but were unaltered in agronomic or grain characteristics. Those intermediate in plant height, in the background of photoperiod sensitivity, also maintained most of the parent's original characteristics. Tillering was improved while spikelet number per panicle was slightly reduced.

Initial evaluation in the tidal swamps indicated that the mutant derivatives were well adapted. However, when seeded at Bandjarmasin, S. Kalimantan, Indonesia, on 25 March, most of the photoperiod-sensitive mutants were about 1 month later than Siyam Kuning. This was unexpected and will be further investigated in 1981 using several dates of planting.

If ethyleneimine is specific in altering culm length, it should be emphasized as a future tool in the improvement of specifically adapted traditional varieties. ■

Effect of flag leaf on grain yield of transplanted rice

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The flag leaf plays an important role in the assimilation and translocation of assimilates in the rice plant, and thus ultimately influences grain yield. Rice varieties may differ in the degree of the flag-leaf influence on grain yield and the importance of the flag leaf at different stages of panicle development.

A study at Allahabad during the 1975 wet season studied the influence of the flag leaf on grain yield in five rice varieties. The flag leaf was removed at panicle emergence, 7 days after panicle emergence, and 14 days after panicle emergence. The grain yields from those treatments and a treatment with intact flag leaves were compared (see table).

The difference in grain yield among

the rice varieties was significant. In all varieties, however, plants with intact flag leaves gave the highest grain yield. Removal of the flag leaf at any stage after panicle emergence caused significant reduction in grain yield. Grain

yield reduction was maximum when the flag leaf was removed immediately after panicle emergence. There was a marked improvement in grain yield in all varieties as the process of flag leaf removal was delayed. ■

Effect of flag leaf removal on grain yield of 5 rice varieties. Allahabad, India.

Rice variety	Grain yield ^a (g/55 tillers)			Flag leaf not removed
	0 d	7 d	14 d	
Sona	99.35	112.78	120.78	141.51
RP79-14	110.14	120.23	122.62	129.31
RP79-5	92.44	93.20	108.89	128.01
Ratna	97.99	101.54	107.54	125.11
Jaya	111.76	126.20	130.12	135.75
Mean	102.33	110.83	117.98	131.93
S.Em.	Varieties = 0.31		Treatments = 0.088	
CD (P = 0.01)	" = 0.86		" = 0.28	

^a Flag leaves were removed 0, 7, and 14 days after panicle emergence.

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